

Impact of Audit Committee Attributes on Earnings Management Practices: Empirical Evidence from Pakistan Stock Exchange

Adnan Faisal¹, Sun Xiufeng^{1*}, Muhammad Safdar², Sattar Khan³, Naveed Khan Walid¹, Aleem Ullah¹

¹ School of Economics and Management, Dalian University of Technology, Dalian 116024, China

² School of Transportation and Logistics, Dalian University of Technology, Dalian 116024, China

³ Institute of Management Science, Peshawar 25100, Pakistan

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*Corresponding Author:
Sun Xiufeng

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Conflicts of Interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

ABSTRACT

This article examines the effect of Audit Committee characteristics such as Independence, Expertise, Size and Diligence on Earnings Management in the light of the recent past (2017) amendment in the Code of Corporate Governance in Pakistan. The study has taken a sample of 172 non-financial companies from Pakistan Stock Exchange to check the amendment's impact on the Audit Committee composition. This study is covering 860 firm years' observations from 2013 to 2017. Pearson Correlation, Descriptive statistics and Random Effect Regression were employed to estimate the results. The study findings reveal that among Audit Committee attributes, expertise in Audit Committee is negative coefficients with both the proxies of Earnings Management. Moreover, the coefficient values -0.171 are significantly negative with 1% in Jones (1991) model and -0.193 in Modified Jones (1995) Model, which indicates that a one percent increase in Audit Committee expertise will reduce Earnings Management by 17 to 19 percent. On the other hand, Independence, Size and Activity are not significantly related to the proxy of Earnings Management. The literature on Audit Committee attributes and Earnings Management is scarce, particularly in Pakistan; therefore, this paper adds its part in corporate governance literature on Pakistani perspective and shows the importance of Audit Committee attributes in monitoring income manipulation. Lastly, the outcomes of this paper can be of particular interest to the developing countries' monitoring authorities and policymakers to ensure the independence and expertise of the Audit Committee.

Keywords: AUDIT COMMITTEE, CORPORATE GOVERNANCE, EARNINGS MANAGEMENT, DISCRETIONARY AND NON-DISCRETIONARY ACCRUAL, RANDOM EFFECT REGRESSION, CODE OF CORPORATE GOVERNANCE, PAKISTAN STOCK EXCHANGE.

1. Introduction

In the corporate governance (hereafter CG) literature, an Audit Committee has received worldwide acclaim during the past two decades due to the well-known global corporate financial scandals (frauds) such as WorldCom, Enron and Xerox, etc., (Sultana, 2015) . Misrepresentations of accounting reports originate from the malpractice of rife Earnings Management (hereafter EM). Yang and Krishnan (2005) argue that regulators worldwide have often shown concerns and reservations about corporate EM. In this regard, Audit Committees (hereafter AC) is considered an essential component in the system of CG. The presence of AC ensures the credibility and transparency of financial statements and checks on managers' financial reporting, including their attempts to distort earnings.

According to Ayemere and Elijah (2015) the fundamental responsibility of corporations and corporate systems worldwide is the true financial reporting representation to its stakeholders. Financial statements representation to all stakeholders on behalf of the corporations is considered a good communication medium. Financial reporting decreases the irregular and imbalanced financial information flow to the external interested parties of the companies. Keeping in view the above point Habbash (2013) argues that active AC ensures the worth and transparency of financial statement reporting. Moreover, according to Duchin, Matsusaka, and Ozbas (2010), the corporations' financial statements' veracity and reliability are determined mainly by effective monitoring mechanisms such as the corporations' AC. An AC plays a critical part in confirming the transparency of the firm's financial statements reporting (Lawrence J. Abbott, Park, & Parker, 2000).

Bergstresser and Philippon (2006) documented that EM practices are made by management. It is made to serve their personal interest such as contractual benefits, bonuses and promotions, etc., rather than shareholders' interest. Such practices violate agency theory's spirits and show a fake picture of the company position to its stakeholders. EM occurred when the company's management uses judgments and the elasticity principles and concepts of accounting standards provided to equal the company's earnings with the desired level of their choice (Mishra & Malhotra, 2016). They further added that EM's practice alters the company's reporting information's worth and transparency and makes hurdles in decision-making choices of the company's stakeholders. In order to prevent EM practices on behalf of the management, an AC is a pivotal tool. An AC with independent and expert members may confirm the veracity and transparency in reporting financial information to the interested parties, which may result to play a fundamental part in the minimization of the discretionary power of management and may encourage the confidence of external stakeholders in the company's affair.

After the above discussion on the AC, the mere presence of an AC is not sufficient to prevent management from the manipulation of financial statements; nevertheless, more emphasis should be given to make it more effective and efficient. To ensure corporate transparency and real disclosure practices in Pakistan, the regulatory body (Security Exchange Commission of Pakistan) has changed the Pakistan Corporate Governance Code time by time to strengthen governance structure and bring uniformity in the corporate

governance practices via Pakistan Stock Exchange listing requirements. Pakistan Corporate Governance Code was launched firstly in 2002 in Pakistan, and then with a passage of time, it was amended such as in 2012, 2017, and 2019 in order to make it more suitable for the current scenario. This code of corporate governance mandates a well independent and expert AC for transparent financial reporting.

This paper emphasizes the important aspect of the “Code of Corporate Governance” (hereafter CCG), which stated that an independent director should chair AC of any corporations in Pakistan. One member should be Financially Literate. It means that the member should have the required experience and qualification of the audit, accounting, and Finance, this feature was added in a recent past amendment in CCG in December 2017. In addition to these two characteristics, Klein (2002) has suggested in his research study that AC size and meetings are also important attributes in constraining EM. He furthered added that expertise in AC and financially literate members in AC are negatively associated with EM. The findings of the study depict that AC independence and expertise effectively mitigate discretionary accruals (Earnings Management proxy), while this study finds no clue whether AC meeting frequency and size have associated with EM. The result of this study supports and in line with the recent amendment in Pakistan CCG, which mandates a well independent and expert AC.

The research study makes three significant contributions to the existing literature. Firstly, (to the best of researchers’ knowledge), the current study is the first research study in the Pakistani context that checks the effect of an AC characteristic on discretionary accruals (EM). Secondly, this study support and recommend the recent amendment in Pakistan Corporate Governance Code, which is about AC independence and expertise. In addition to this, a fully independent and expert AC will abstain management to engage in EM practice, which will result in authentic and credible financial information to all the stakeholders. Lastly, this study is the first research study to investigate AC related recommendations in Pakistan Corporate Governance Code with EM.

The rest of the paper is structured as follows. In section 2, the related literature about AC and EM is discussed and ends with the hypotheses. After that in section 3, the research design, methods, variables estimation, and definition are discussed, section 4 shows the empirical results. Section 5 outlines the conclusion and this paper ends with limitations and future research.

2. Context of the Study

Pakistan is a common law country, where many institutions are working under different regulatory regimes, but the most important institutions are financial and non-financial institutions. Financial institutions are commercial & Islamic banks, insurance companies, mutual funds, leasing companies, and Modarabas. The principal regulator for financial institutions such as commercial banks & Islamic banks is the “State Bank of Pakistan” (hereafter SBP). On the other hand, non-financial institutions such as manufacturing companies are mainly controlled by “Securities Exchange Commission of Pakistan” (hereafter SECP). Companies are registered with SECP, either public limited companies or private limited companies. Some are not registered

or listed on “Pakistan Stock Exchange” (hereafter PSX) and some are registered or listed on PSX in public limited companies. SECP issued the Code of Corporate Governance in 2002 in Pakistan, which was implemented through PSX listed requirements. In this first CG code, the establishment of an audit committee was encouraged but not made mandatory. After the implementation of the CG code in 2002, various shortcomings and drawbacks were pointed out in it by policymakers, international institutions and concerned parties, which stimulated the SECP to revise it in 2012 with the mandatory formation of an audit committee in the companies registered under the companies’ ordinance 1984 with SECP. In which it was encouraging to be chair by an independent non-executive director. In addition to this, in 2017, the Code of Corporate Governance was again revised with the mandatory clauses of chair independence and expert member in the audit committee. Due to the changes as mentioned earlier, which is made in CCG in Pakistan, we are motivated to carry out this research study in order to check the usefulness of audit committee features on earnings management, which are prevalent in Pakistani companies, and to investigate whether these changes which were introduced in various codes an audit committee improve financial reporting quality and decrease earnings management via discretionary accruals or not. After collecting data from the 172 audit committee firms, the study results show that AC independence and expertise effectively mitigate discretionary accruals (Earnings Management proxy). In contrast, this study finds no clue whether AC meeting frequency and size have associated with EM. This study supports and is in line with the recent amendment in Pakistan CCG, which mandates a well independent and expert AC.

3. Literature Review

The practice of EM is the management reporting strategy to manipulate company financial records in order to achieve their pre-determined financial objective. According to Qamhan, Che Haat, Hashim, and Salleh (2018) EM practices on behalf of the management result in less reliable accounting information that does not reflect the company's real financial position. Juhmani (2017) maintained that management uses EM either for the company’s interest or their own vested interest; this action of the management results in an agency problem. Agency theory has clearly mentioned the direct link between management opportunist behavior (earnings management) and corporate governance mechanisms (Audit committee). It further proposes the system of corporate governance to minimize the agency cost for the company (Jensen & Meckling, 1976; McColgan, 2001).

The existence of an AC is considered an effective tool of CG structure, and it helps to monitor management’s role in preparing financial reporting (Mohd Saleh, Mohd Iskandar, & Mohid Rahmat, 2007). Various researchers have documented the effective role of AC in ensuring the quality and accuracy of financial information via constant monitoring mechanisms (Lawrence J. Abbott et al., 2000; Fama & Jensen, 1983; Khan et al., 2020; Klein, 2002).

The study of Khan et al. (2020) investigated the role of AC effectiveness in reducing earnings management in 169 Pakistani firms for the period of 2013 to 2017 and finds that AC attributes measured through an index

has an effective role in reducing discretionary accruals (EM Proxy) in Pakistan Stock Exchange-listed firms.

According to Klein (2002) and Xie, Davidson III, and DaDalt (2003), CG's practice could be linked with transparent and reliable financial statements. He further stated that CG practice reduces the cost/conflict of agency and enables management to provide accurate information to the company's stakeholders and prevent them from engaging in EM practices.

3.1. Independence of an AC and Earnings Management

Independence is one of the key characteristics of AC. The independence in AC really matters in curbing the opportunist behavior of management. The independent director in the committee is one of the vital elements linked with AC's effectiveness (Ayemere & Elijah 2015). So due to the importance of an independent director in AC, the recent corporate governance code-related amendment, which was implemented in Pakistan in 2017, made it mandatory that there must be one independent director in AC and it should chair the committee of an audit. Moreover, that independent director should not be in any other position in the Board. The director's independence means that a person who holds the position of director in a company must not have any relationship with the management and independent from the company's management.

The literature on the concerned topic depicts that independence in AC is negatively related to the proxy of EM. Klein (2002) documented that AC independence has a negative relationship with discretionary accruals. The more independence in the AC will show better corporate governance than less independence in AC (Xie et al., 2003). Blue Ribbon Committee, 1999 findings showed that independent AC could encourage a more transparent reporting process. According to Lawrence J. Abbott, Parker, and Peters (2004) the practice of income smoothing in corporations reduces if there is a presence of independence in the AC.

On the other hand, the study of Chen, Cussatt, and Gunny (2020) documented that outside independent directors cannot be efficient monitors of the management to reduce earnings management. the reason behind this assumption may be the information disadvantage, they further added that as compare to insider outsiders(independent), directors may not have information to deter management from earnings manipulation. Consequently, the first hypothesis of the study is,

H1: Independence in Audit Committee is negatively related to EM practices.

3.2. Audit Committee Diligence and Earnings Management

The CCG in Pakistan requires from the listed companies as a listing requirement to hold a meeting every quarter in a financial year. The frequency of meetings enables audit members to watch over the preceding of the business' financial statements frequently and effectively accomplish the monitoring role assigned to them. According to Xie et al. (2003) those committees which held meetings more frequently during a financial year are associated with a more proficient monitoring process. In addition, Lawrence J. Abbott et al. (2004) depicted in his study that those committees who hold four meetings per year have a negative

relation with income smoothing process (earnings management). Moreover, the prime role of an AC is to make certain reliability and transparency in annual financial statement reporting; this function can be achieved if the committee meets frequently. Klein (2002). However, a number of research studies in literature showed no association between EM practices and frequency of AC meetings Ayemere and Elijah (2015). So, the literature gives mixed results regarding this phenomenon. Hence, the second hypothesis of the study will predict a negative association between meeting frequency and EM.

H2: Activity in Audit Committee is negatively related to discretionary accruals (a proxy of EM).

3.3. Expertise in Audit committee and Earnings Management

The most prominent characteristic for an AC's effectiveness is the expertise of the members of an AC. This quality of financial expertise has received worldwide consideration in current years. The 2017 code of corporate governance in Pakistan has specified that in AC there must be one member who should have financial expertise. The term 'financial literate (expertise)' means a person who has the membership of a Security Exchanges Commission of Pakistan (SECP) recognized body of professional accountants or has a higher degree in Finance from a Higher Education Commission (HEC) recognized university or equivalent institution. In addition, the Sarbanes-Oxley Act of (2002) suggested that at least one should have financial knowledge in AC members. Juhmani (2017) argues that it is generally accepted worldwide that the main obligation of an AC is to review and check the companies' financial statements; hence, AC members must have financial and accounting background. According to Adams, Jiang, and Finance (2020), expert members in Board improve firm financial performance, resulting in improved financial reporting and less earnings management. Therefore, the AC members' financial experience and expertise can increase the effectiveness of monitoring, detecting, and averting EM practices in the corporations. Moreover, Inaam and Khamoussi (2016) documented in their research paper that financially expert members in AC have an opposite (negative) relationship with EM's management practice. A Pakistani study of textile sectors one of Pakistan's biggest sector shows that expert members reduce earnings manipulation. Keeping in view the above-mentioned literature review the third hypothesis of the study proposes that accounting and financial expertise would result in less EM. Thus, the hypothesis is,

H3: The Expertise member's AC reduces EM in the Pakistan listed companies.

3.4. Earnings Management and Size of the Audit Committee

As a listing requirement for the companies in Pakistan, it is compulsory that listed companies should have three members in AC comprising of non-executive directors and at least one independent director. This rule is consistent with Blue Ribbon Committee (1999) recommendation and SOX act (2002). According to Vafeas (2005) the size of an AC is really matters in improving financial statement reporting because the larger the size of an ACs the more will be the advantage of having a greater knowledge base and experience, which can be utilize more effectively in monitoring financial statements. Mansor, Che-Ahmad, Ahmad-

Zaluki, and Osman (2013) argue that size of an AC is instrumental in decreasing income smoothing process in companies. In addition, Kent, Routledge, and Stewart (2010) documented that larger the committee size the less will be EM and higher the quality of financial statements. In the study Musallam (2020) added that AC size improves firm financial performance, which may be linked to improve financial reporting quality and improved financial reporting quality reduces earnings manipulations. From the preceding discussion, the last hypothesis of our study can be proposed in the following words.

H4: The strength of the members in AC and EM is negatively associated.

4. Research Design and Method

4.1. The Population and Sample of the Study

Pakistan Stock Exchange (hereafter PSX) listed companies is the population of this research study. The data collection period is from 2013 -2017. The total listed companies in PSX are 543 by August 2020, out of which 129 are financial companies and the remaining 414 is non-financial companies. During the data collection process, 110 companies were left out due to non-availability of annual reports, missing corporate governance information, delisted from PSX, or declared defaulter by the authorities of PSX; furthermore, those companies were also left out whose audit committee related information were either not available or not sufficient to proceed with it, after applying the above-mentioned filters 172 firms were selected for this research study in order to investigate the objectives of the study. The detail of sample selection procedure is given in the Table No 1. The sample size of the study is 172 non-financial companies consisting of almost all the sectors of PSX. The detail of PSX sectors, total number of firms in each sector, percentage of each sectors to total firms and sample per cent age is given in detail in the Annexure No 1.

Table 1 Procedures of Sample Selection

Sample Firms

Total Non-financial firms listed in the PSX in November 2020	414
Less: Annual Reports Missing Defaulter and Delisted firms for the said period	(110)
	304
Less: Firms with the missing Audit Committee information	(132)
Firms selected for the study	172

4.2 Description of Variables

4.2.1 Dependent Variable

The dependent variable of this study is Earnings Management (EM) estimated by discretionary accruals.

This study has used Jones Model (1991) and Modified Jones Model By Dechow, Sloan, and Sweeney (1995) to estimate and detect EM. According to Haider, Ali, and Sadiq (2012) discretionary accruals (DA) can be estimated by two different approaches or methods one is taking the values from balance sheet, which is called the balance sheet approach, and the other is taking values from cash flow statements in order to estimate total accruals which is called cash flow statement approach.

The concerned literature depicted that most of the researcher has used cash flow statement for estimating EM (Haider et al., 2012; Zalata, Tauringana, & Tingbani, 2018). In this study cash flow statement approach has been used to calculate total accruals (TA). Discretionary accrual (DA) is obtained by deducting Non-discretionary accruals (NDA) from TA. The following steps are used to obtain the value of DA.

First, to calculate the value of TA, this is calculated by the following equation:

$$TA_{it} = NI_{it} - CFO_{it} \quad (1)$$

Whereas:

TA_{it} = Total Accruals at t period for firm i

NI_{it} = Net Income before tax at t period for firm i

CFO_{it} = Net Cash Flow from Operating Activities at t period for firm i

When the TA has calculated, then the value of NDA will be calculated, the procedure of which under the Jones (1991) and Modified Jones Model (1995) is described in equation 2 & 3 as follows,

$$TA_{it} / LA_{it} = \alpha(1/LA_{it} - 1) + \beta_1(\Delta REV_{it} / LA_{it} - 1) + \beta_2(PPE_{it} / LA_{it} - 1) + \varepsilon_{it} \quad (2)$$

$$TA_{it} / LA_{it} = \alpha(1/LA_{it} - 1) + \beta_1(\Delta REV_{it} - \Delta REC_{it} / LA_{it} - 1) + \beta_2(PPE_{it} / LA_{it} - 1) + \varepsilon_{it} \quad (3)$$

Whereas:

TA_{it} = The value of Total Accruals obtained in equation 1

LA_{it} = Lagged value of total assets for a company i for time t

ΔREV_{it} = Delta revenues mean ($REV_{it} - REV_{it-1}$)

ΔREC_{it} = Delta receivable means ($REC_{it} - REC_{it-1}$)

PPE_{it} = The value property, plant and equipment before deprecation for a company i for time t

$\beta_0, \beta_1, \beta_2,$ = Parameters in the model

ε_{it} = Residual

After solving equation number 2, the value of NDA is obtained, thus for calculating the value of DA, value of NDA will be subtracted from TA.

4.2.2. The Explanatory Variables and Control variables

The Explanatory variables for this research paper are AC independence, AC activity, AC size and AC expertise. The data related to independent variables have been taken out from annual financial reports of the

concerned companies. The independence of an AC is effective in constraining EM; this phenomenon has been documented in numerous research studies such as (Bedard & Johnstone, 2004; Vafeas, 2005) etc. Moreover, Ebrahim (2007) argued that independence in AC is effective in constraining EM. Mansor et al. (2013) and Kent et al. (2010) added that the bigger the size of AC the greater will be the quality of financial reporting. In addition to this, the activity of AC is also effective in controlling EM. Inaam and Khamoussi (2016) documented that AC activity has a significant impact on EM. AC expertise is also an important aspect for monitoring financial reports (Qamhan et al., 2018). Studies such as Xie et al. (2003) and Bedard and Johnstone (2004) reported that AC expertise influences the financial reporting process, and it is negatively associated with the proxy of EM. Apart from the Predictors Board's size, expertise, independence, diversity, and meetings have been taken as control variables. In addition to this return on assets, the firm's size and leverage are additional control variables used in this research study. The detail of the control and independents variables is given below in Table 1.

4.3. Research Model of the Study

The EM phenomenon among Pakistani listed firms is prevailing, as investigated by (Ilyas, Khan, & Urooge, 2019; Kamran & Shah, 2014; N. Khan & Shah, 2019; Shah, Rashid, & Malik, 2020). Moreover, SECP has introduced new clauses for strengthening audit committees to improve financial reporting quality and curb earnings management. The clause of audit committee chair independence and expertise of a member in audit committee may help restrain management for earnings manipulation in the Pakistani context. Furthermore, the study of Khan et al. (2020) depicted that AC effectiveness is very instrumental in reducing discretionary accruals. Based on the above discussion, we assume that AC attributes such as Size, Meeting frequency, independence, and expert members may have a role in reducing earnings manipulation in Pakistani listed firms. In order to check that whether AC attributes affect EM following research model is implemented.

$$EM_{IT} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 ASIZE_{IT} + \beta_2 AD_{IT} + \beta_3 AEXP_{IT} + \beta_4 AIND_{IT} + \beta_5 BEXP_{it} + \beta_6 BI_{it} + \beta_7 BD_{it} + \beta_8 BM_{it} + \beta_9 BS + \beta_{10} FS_{IT} + \beta_{11} LEVE_{IT} + \beta_{12} ROA_{IT} + \varepsilon_{IT} \quad (4)$$

Whereas:

- EM_{IT} = The absolute value of Discretionary Accruals of Jones (1991) & Modified Jones Model (1995)
- $AIND_{IT}$ = AC Independence
- $AEXP_{IT}$ = AC Expertise
- $ASIZE_{IT}$ = The size of AC
- AD_{IT} = The Number of the meeting by AC
- $BEXP_{IT}$ = Expertise in Board
- BI_{IT} = Board Independence

BD_{IT}	= Board Diversity
BM_{IT}	= Board Meeting
BS_{IT}	=Board Size
FS_{IT}	= Log of total Assets
$LEVE_{IT}$	= Long term debt divided by shareholder equity is the ratio of leverage
ROA_{IT}	= The obtained from Net Income by lagged Total Assets
$\beta_0, \beta_1, \beta_2, \beta_3, \beta_4, \beta_5, \beta_6$ ETC	= Parameters of the model
ε_{IT}	= Residual

Table 2 Variables definitions

Variables	Definition	Literature support	Test
EM	Earnings Management estimated by Jones Model (1991) and Modified Jones Model (1995)	(Dechow et al., 1995; Jones, 1991)	Predicted Variable
AC Independence	The independent member by total member in the Board.	(Ayemere & Elijah 2015)	H1
AC Diligence	The figure of the total meeting held in a year by the AC or Meeting Frequency	(Ayemere & Elijah 2015; Xie et al., 2003)	H2
AC Expertise	The proportion of directors having accounting and finance knowledge by total directors.	(Qamhan et al., 2018)	H3
AC Size	The strength of the directors in the AC.	(Chandrasegaram, Rahimansa, Rahman, Abdullah, & Mat, 2013; Lin, Li, & Yang, 2006)	H4
Board's Expertise	The number of board member who have Finance and accounting knowledge by total board members.	(Bala & Kumai, 2015)	Control
Board's Indep	Independent directors divided by Total directors in the Board.	(Chouaibi, Harres, & Ben Brahim, 2016; Zhou, Owusu-Ansah, & Maggina, 2018)	Control
Board's Diversity	The ratio of women in the Board	(Isa & Farouk, 2018)	Control
Board's Meeting	Total number of meeting in the one financial year	(Chouaibi, Harres, & Brahim, 2018)	Control
Board's Size	Total member in the Board of directors.	(Bala & Kumai, 2015; Kao & Chen, 2004)	Control
Firm Size	Log of total assets	(Mohd Saleh et al., 2007; Qamhan et al., 2018; Young, 1998)	Control
Financial Leverage	Long term debt divided by shareholder equity	(Qamhan et al., 2018; Zhou et al., 2018)	Control
ROA	Net profit by total assets	(Mohammed, Che-Ahmad, & Malek, 2019; Zalata et al., 2018)	Control

5. Data Analysis and Discussion

The following Table No.3 presents the detail of summary statistics of the study's variables. It includes the values of total observations, mean, standard deviation, minimum value and maximum value. According to the below Table, the Jones Model (1991) values hereafter JM are as follows; 607 represents total observation, minimum value of it is -4.15 and Maximum value is 3.775. The values of Modified Jones Model (1995) hereafter MJM are as follows; its total observation is 607, Standard Deviation is .323 and minimum & maximum values are -4.283 & 3.761. The Size of AC is a minimum of 3 members while maximum of 7 members with an average of 3.48 members across the sample size listed firms of PSX. Moreover, the average number of meetings in a year of the selected firms are 4.29, with a minimum of 3 and maximum of 12 meetings per year. The summary statistics table shows that approximately 30 percent ACs have financial expertise, while on the other hand, approximately 31 percent ACs have independent directors. According to these findings, this will be the need of the hour to increase the strength of independent and expert members in the audit committees to impose in true spirit the recent past amendment in CCG in Pakistan in order to achieve its targeted objectives.

Table 3 Summary statistics

Variables	N	Mean	S.Dev	Min	Max
JM	607	0	.319	-4.15	3.775
MJM	607	0	.323	-4.283	3.761
AC Size	841	3.488	.773	3	7
AC Diligence	839	4.297	.786	3	12
AC Expertise	806	.309	.261	0	1
AC Independence	840	.311	.199	0	1
Board's Expertise	836	.253	.188	0	.857
Board's Indep..	838	.173	.133	0	.778
Board's Diversity	835	.374	.484	0	1
Board's Meetings	835	5.329	1.737	2	17
Board's Size	835	8.216	1.553	6	15
Firm size	755	6.839	.734	3.99	9.51
ROA	845	7.238	13.803	-88.45	123.95
Leverage	739	2.975	5.43	0	86.08

In Table No. 4, Pearson correlation test results are presented, showing correlation coefficients of the study variables including predicted residual coefficient. The Pearson correlation test findings demonstrate that AC expertise is negatively related with proxies of EM the values of -0.077, -0.067, and -0.053, which shows that expert members in AC reduce earnings manipulation in selected PSX listed firms. In addition to this, the AC diligence is also negatively related with the proxy of the Jones Model (1991); the value of -0.001 indicates that relationship. In addition to this, the correlation between the control variable leverage and the proxies of EM is negatively related, which depicts that firms that have debt burden are negatively related with EM. Moreover, the Table of correlation matrix shows no problem of Multicollinearity because the correlation

coefficient values are very small (less than the threshold value 0.60) for all the independent variables; we can say that there is no Multicollinearity problem, which is subsequently confirmed by the test of VIF. In addition to this, we have predicted the residual coefficient and then added it to the variables in the correlation matrix to check the problem of Endogeneity. The results of the correlation matrix show that coefficients of predicted errors term are very small with all of the independent variables, which show that there is no problem of Endogeneity.

Table 4 Pearson Correlation results

Variables	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15
JM (1)	1.000														
MJM (2)	-----	1.000													
AC Size (3)	0.005	0.032	1.000												
AC Diligence (4)	-0.001	0.014	0.147	1.000											
AC Expertise(5)	-0.077	-0.067	0.173	0.093	1.000										
AC Independence(6)	0.013	0.007	-0.035	0.019	0.170	1.000									
Board's Expertise(7)	0.023	0.017	0.086	0.050	0.585	0.223	1.000								
Board's Indepen.(8)	0.024	0.034	0.076	0.133	0.207	0.664	0.182	1.000							
Board's Diversity(9)	0.059	0.054	-0.045	-0.065	-0.067	-0.082	0.063	-0.094	1.000						
Board's Diligence(10)	-0.026	-0.042	0.046	0.148	0.036	0.195	0.042	0.265	0.013	1.000					
Board's Size(11)	0.030	0.056	0.437	0.104	0.177	0.020	0.056	0.163	-0.045	-0.002	1.000				
Firm size(12)	-0.032	0.065	0.319	0.194	0.323	0.088	0.090	0.234	-0.039	0.115	0.293	1.000			
ROA (13)	0.012	0.030	0.259	0.018	0.199	0.008	0.185	0.069	0.077	-0.040	0.159	0.299	1.000		
Leverage (14)	-0.033	-0.040	-0.096	0.045	-0.064	0.052	-0.009	0.017	-0.043	0.038	-0.055	-0.015	-0.186	1.000	
Residual (15)	0.261	0.275	0.021	-0.002	-0.295	0.048	0.090	0.094	0.225	-0.100	0.114	-0.124	0.045	-0.126	1.000

In Table No. 5, the results of Random Effect Regression have been presented. The estimation results show the effect of independent variables such as the size of AC, meeting of AC, independence of AC, and AC expertise on EM estimated by (Jones, 1991) and (Dechow et al., 1995) models. In addition to this, control variable such as Board's expertise, independence, diversity, size and meetings are also included with return on assets, financial leverage and firm size. The Random Effect Model selection is based on the basis of the Hausman Specification Test by using STATA 14 software (between Fixed and Random Effect model). The overall estimated model is significant with Prob > Chi2 statistic value of 0.0287.

Table 5 The Hausman Specification Test

Test Summary	χ^2	Prob
Cross-section Random	17.14	0.0287

Table 6 Regression Analysis (Random Effect Model)

Predicted Variable (EM)	Jones Model (1991)		Modified Jones Model (1995)	
	Coefficients	Std. Err. (T-Values)	Coefficients	Std. Err. (T-Values)
AC Size	1.011	0.021 (.53)	0.014	0.021 (0.68)
AC Diligence	0.010	0.012 (0.79)	0.008	0.012 (0.67)
AC Expertise	-0.171	0.061 (-2.82***)	-0.193	0.070 (-2.75***)
AC Independence	0.010	0.068 (0.882)	0.002	0.063 (0.03)
Control Variables				
Board's Expertise	0.117	0.099 (1.18)	0.114	0.102 (1.13)
Board's Indep	0.204	0.122 (1.68*)	0.227	.124 (1.83*)
Board's Diversity	0.032	0.020 (1.63)	0.031	0.021 (1.49)
Board's Meeting	0.002	0.008 (-0.05)	-0.002	0.009 (0.59)
Board's Size	0.005	0.009 (0.57)	0.006	0.012 (0.59)
Firm Size	0.021	0.032 (0.64)	0.74	0.043 (1.73*)
ROA	0.0025	0.032 (0.61)	0.001	0.003 (0.46)
Leverage	-0.002	0.002 (-1.08)	-0.003	0.003(-1.10)
Constant	-0.354	0.279 (-1.27)	-0.704	0.314 (-2.24**)
ID	Y	Y	Y	Y
YD	Y	Y	Y	Y
Prob > Chi2	0.000***		0.000***	
Number of Obs.	531		531	

Overall R-Sq	0.105	0.120	
Number of Groups	172		172

Note: ***, ** and * refers to significance level at 1%, 5% and 10%

ID, is for industry dummy, YD is for Year Dummy and Y for Yes

In the Table 6, the results of regression analysis (Random effect) is displaying by taking AC attributes as independent variables and absolute values of Jones (1991) and dechow modified it 1995 Modified Jones model (1995) the proxies of EM is a dependent variable with a bunch of control variables. The results of Table 6 indicates that among AC attributes, expertise in AC is negative coefficients with both the proxies of EM, which implies that expert members in AC reduce earnings manipulation, which is in line with (Agwor & Jane Osinachi, 2018; Bedard & Johnstone, 2004; Xie et al., 2003; Zalata et al., 2018). Moreover, the coefficient values -0.171 are significantly negative with 1% in Jones (1991) model and -0.193 in Modified Jones (1995) Model, which indicates that a one percent increase in AC expertise will reduce EM by 17 to 19 percent.

Additionally, in control variables, leverage has negatively related with the proxy of EM, while the firm size is positively associated with EM. In terms of individual coefficients of independent variables, AC expertise has significant coefficients while other characteristics have not significant coefficients. Hence, the coefficient values of AC expertise show that AC's members' accounting and finance knowledge has an impact on decreasing EM, which supported our *H3*.

On the other hand, independence, size and meeting attributes of AC have an insignificant relationship with EM but positive coefficients; hence due to the result of the model H1, H2 and H4 is not supported and accepted. Although AC independence is widely regarded as one of the important feature in AC worldwide due to family-oriented business, ownership concentration and minimum or by name presence of independent directors in Pakistani firms could be the possible reasons for these findings. Moreover, this study's findings are consistent with the study of (Chen et al., 2020) documented that outside independent directors cannot be efficient monitors of the management to reduce earnings management. The reason behind this assumption may be the information disadvantage; they further added that as compare to insider outsiders(independent) directors may not have information to deter management from earnings manipulation. The overall result suggested that independence, size and meeting frequency of AC is not effective in constraining discretionary accruals (DA), while on the other hand, effective AC monitoring is associated with AC members accounting and finance knowledge.

6. Conclusions

This research paper investigated the relationship between AC attributes such as meetings, size, independence, and expertise with DA as EM's proxy. The population of the study was listed non-financial companies of the Pakistan Stock Exchange. The data for this research paper was gathered from 172

companies after leaving financial companies and those whose data were missing. The data period of this study is five years ranging from 2013 to 2017. The findings of this research study documented the proof that the expertise of AC members is significantly negatively associated with DA proxy of EM. Furthermore, the evidence revealed that AC those members who have the knowledge of accounting and Finance has an impact on EM proxy. In addition to this, the average independence of 31 percent in AC of the selected PSX listed non-financial firms show that its role of curbing earnings manipulation is invisible. It may be due to the recommendatory provision of independence in the Board of directors by SECP. Moreover, the study results present that AC meetings, independence and size are not negatively related to the proxy of EM.

Similar to other research studies, this research study also suffers and has some shortcomings. Firstly, the finding of this paper is related to Pakistani listed firms, so its results cannot be generalized to other stock exchange companies such as developed countries. Secondly, the study sample size is based on non-financial firms; hence, its result may not be generalized to financial firms. Lastly, the sample size of the study may not be considered and used as a rule of thumb to explain other studies' findings. Due to this research study's limitations, it provides the directions to further researchers to check the impact after the mandatory independence in Board and Audit Committee in the Code of Corporate Governance in Pakistan. Moreover, future researchers may consider taking more attributes of an AC with some other variables of CG in order to check the impact on EM or other variables across different sectors or with large sample size and different time periods.

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